

EcoEvoRxiv partners with the California Digital Library to re-launch preprint service on the Janeway platform

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The EcoEvoRxiv community and the eScholarship Publishing program at the California Digital Library (CDL) are delighted to announce a partnership to host the EcoEvoRxiv preprint server at the CDL. The re-launch of EcoEvoRxiv is scheduled to take place during [International Open Access Week 2022](#) (October 24-30).

“This relaunch marks a new start and a milestone for EcoEvoRxiv,” says Shinichi Nakagawa, one of its founders. “It is now widely recognised among ecologists, as well as evolutionary and conservation biologists because of their support.”

CDL will host EcoEvoRxiv on [Janeway](#), an open source publishing platform developed by the Centre for Technology and Publishing and the Open Library of Humanities at Birkbeck University of London. The EcoEvoRxiv moderation team will maintain ownership and control over the preprint server, while the eScholarship Publishing team will contribute to the development, support, and maintenance of the Janeway platform.

“We are delighted to host EcoEvoRxiv at the University of California,” says Catherine Mitchell, Director of Publishing, Archives, and Digitization at CDL. “Preprint servers continue to prove their worth in providing rapid access to research findings and reimagining the scholarly communication space in ways that benefit both research and the global community. Supporting EcoEvoRxiv is aligned with the values and the goals of eScholarship’s open access publishing program, and it’s a great opportunity for UC to continue to build its preprint server program in alignment with the interests of our researchers.”

[EcoEvoRxiv launched in January 2019](#) on the [Center for Open Science](#)’s Open Science Framework. To date, it hosts more than 900 empirical, theoretical, and review preprints in a range of ecology, evolution, and conservation topics. It is the second preprint service hosted by CDL on Janeway, joining [EarthArXiv](#), which [re-launched on CDL's Janeway instance in October 2020](#).

October 2022 also marks another important change for EcoEvoRxiv as it has officially become part of [SORTEE](#), the Society for Open, Reliable, and Transparent Ecology and Evolutionary biology.

EcoEvoRxiv authors and readers should expect minimal disruptions to the service, as well as improved functionality, when the site re-launches later this month. Authors will need to re-register in Janeway to regain access to their submitted preprints.